

Analysis of Level of Relevance Competence of Higher Education Graduates and Supporting Factors with Employment

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ABSTRACT

Current job opportunities are more oriented toward the competence of a person, so Higher Education Institutions must prepare curriculums based on competency so that graduates are competent and can meet work criteria, as well as can also reduce the percentage of unemployed. Purposed this research to the relevance level and find out the supporting factors of Management graduates at Makassar State University. These research subjects are Management Study Program graduates from 2018-2021 has worked and the personnel section, HRD, or recruitment team where graduates work. Research results based on indicators, 1) the speed of alumni getting jobs based on skills; 2) job profile, position, or workload; 3) Ability to complete work; and 4) programmed courses benefits in lectures are 53.12%, can be concluded that the level of relevance is quite relevant between Management Study Program graduates to the needs of employment. As well as supported factors so that management graduates quickly get a job are work experience/internship, organizational experience, soft skills, teamwork ability, project management ability, and competency certification.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Unemployment is an important issue in employment. Unemployment can be said as a product that is not absorbed in the labor market in the available labor force. Job seekers continue to increase yearly in line with population growth and cannot be absorbed by the relatively limited availability of job opportunities. Therefore, graduates had to choose between idealism and realism. Choose to stay in a scant suitable job or become one of many intellectually unemployed [1]. High unemployment rates cause not only economic but also social problems, like social insecurity and poverty [2]. Handling the response will involve many aspects that will affect national policy. Classified as unemployed are residents who have lost their jobs but are looking for a job or preparing to start a new business, residents who feel they cannot find a job and are not looking for a job, or residents who have been accepted for work, but have not yet started work [3].

According to BPS Statistic Indonesia (2022), the number of reactions until August 2022 has reached 8.42 million people. This means that there has been an increase of around 1.49 million people when compared to the situation in February 2020 of 6.93 million [4]. This is because the needs of the job market do not match the criteria, specifications, and competencies of job seekers. One of them is educational

background. Education is a forum for coaching before entering the world of work as well, wider job opportunities, can improve living standards and obtain a certain status in society [5]. In addition, education has a close relationship with productivity. This means that the higher the education, the higher the work productivity and the lower the education, the slower the productivity [6].

With the progress of the times, educational paradigms and systems must meet the demand of the times [7]. Education must meet the needs of the world of work and business in a competency-oriented manner. One of the educational institutions is Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). Higher Education Institutions are a picture of education after secondary education, which puts pressure on academic and professional abilities development as a prerequisite to entering the world of work [8]. HEIs play an important role in producing graduates with the knowledge and qualifications that can drive the nation's development. In this regard, strengthening higher education has ended up being a countrywide approach to boom competitiveness within the global market. Higher education is seen as an important source of human capital that supports regional and global development[1]. According to UNESCO (2022), HEIs enrollment increased from 23.8 million in 2015 to 25.5

million in 2020 [9]. This reflects the global movement to develop a knowledge-based economy. Furthermore, higher education is also a part of the national education system, which plays an important role in educating the nation's life and increasing human competitiveness in all fields. The government and the private sector contribute to realizing equitable and affordable higher education.

The government has endeavored to ensure that education is provided according to the needs of the working world, in particular by developing an education characterized by linkages and equivalence, as well as competency-based [2]. Thus, current education must be competency-oriented so that tertiary institutions produce quality graduates who are competent according to the job market's needs. Therefore, the competencies possessed by graduates must be satisfied with what is needed. The development of science and technology creates the need for an employment dynamic without the need to wait for the readiness of the world of education, so the world of education must quickly adapt to these changes. College graduates must also be prepared to face the world of work as well as graduates who can think intellectually, be innovative, disciplined, and diligent. That way, college graduates must be equipped with an education that can develop their personality both through up-to-date concepts, patterns, and models. For this, it is necessary to know what supporting factors can make it easier for graduates to get a job.

Besides that, it is also necessary to look at the level of relevance of graduate competencies in the world of work. To provide qualification and competency solutions such as what is needed in the world of work, universities will later provide the required method or curriculum [10]. The curriculum must show results on the quality of graduates that impact society after a while in that environment [11]. So that the gap does not widen and creates instability, it is hoped that it can reduce the unemployment rate of college graduates.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Competence of Graduates

The word competence means skill or ability. Competence is ability or knowledge followed by a basic assessment of thinking or habits. On the site, competence is human behavior (skills) that leads to successful organisational performance. The higher the competency of a person, the better the performance will be. Vice versa, the lower a person's competency, the lower the performance will be. Therefore, competence must be continuously honed so that everyone can do their job well and become professional[12]. Meanwhile, Boulter, Dalziel, and Hill (2003) explain competence is a basic characteristic of a person that allows the superior ability to gain in a job, roles and or certain conditions. The embodiment of knowledge (cognitive), attitudes and values (affective), and

skills (psychomotor) in thinking and working so that they can accept the problems they face[13].

Ordinance of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 49 of 2014 stipulates standard units including National Education Standards and National Standards Higher Education [14]. This regulation becomes the legal basis for the formulation of Learning Outcomes, one of which is the Graduate Competency Standards. Graduate Competency Standards are criteria minimum for qualifications ability graduates including knowledge, skills, and attitudes, according to learning outcomes with qualification levels contained in the Indonesian National Qualifications Framework.

B. Relevance

According to Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia (2015), it is said that relevance is a relationship, suitability and linkage that has a purpose and can be used directly as needed [15]. In an adjective, relevance is the relationship between what is happening or being talked about, which is good and following a certain purpose. In addition, relevance is the ability of information to assist users in making decisions when faced with several alternative choices[16]. Meanwhile, in the meaning of a noun, it means the magnitude of the relationship between something and what is happening or being talked. Besides that, education relevance is the level of linkages of the objectives or results of program output in terms of ideals with the support of the accuracy from the elements of input, process, and output.

C. Job Availability

Employment is the availability of work or jobs that can be filled with labor. Employment is a place for job opportunities (demand for labor) for job seekers[17]. The availability of employment is related to efforts by the government to create investment climate opportunities. If investment increases, it will increase production business activities which will increase employment availability.

Providing jobs is well accepted as one of the solutions to public policy for social problems like poverty, broken families, physical and mental health, and others. At times, the simple availability of a job is often not enough to meet the economic, social, and psychological needs that lead people to seek more decent jobs. In this way, employment providers must think apart from providing adequate employment opportunities and must also provide benefits that can meet the needs of each worker[18].

D. Supporting Factors

Supporting factors are all factors that encourage, support, launch, assist and accelerate an achievement that we want[19]. In addition, supporting factors are also things that influence something to develop, advance, add and be more than previously[20]. Meaning these supporting factors facilitate to support of individual, group, and skill behavior.

III. METHODOLOGY

A qualitative method with a descriptive approach is used as the type of research used. This research was used because of its natural characteristics as a source of direct data, the process is more concerned than the outcome, as well as analysis in this study tends to be inductive and essential [21]. In addition, the descriptive approach examines in depth, detail, and intensively both an individual, an institution, certain symptoms to a narrow subject area [22]. The variables studied include the level relevance of graduates is the level of conformity jobs obtained by Management graduates with their educational background and expertise.

The research subjects in this study were graduates of the Makassar State University Management Study Program from 2018 to 2021 and HRD, the Recruitment Team, or the personnel department of the company where the Management Study Program graduates worked. Snowball sampling was used as a data collection technique from the data tracer study majors, as many as 12 people. The data analysis technique in this study consisted of three stages: 1) data reduction to summarize, select, and focus on important things to find patterns; 2) data display is carried out after obtaining a pattern

which is presented in the form of charts, brief descriptions, flowcharts, relationships between categories and the like; 3) Conclusion Drawing is a new finding that has never existed or a finding that is still dim and becomes clear when it has been examined [21].

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. General Description of Respondents

The respondents sampled in this study were 12 people, consisting of 8 alumni who worked as government, private, and entrepreneurial employees, and 4 who were part of the staffing department, HRD, or the Recruitment Team where they worked. Before going into the discussion about the level of relevance of the competence of Management Study Program graduates to the needs of employment and its supporting factors, this paper first discusses the general description of the respondents. In this case, graduate respondents are described based on five characteristics, namely, gender, age, graduate force, position, and length of work. At the same time, supervisor respondents are described based on gender and position.

Table I. General Description of Respondents

No.	Information	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
Management Study Program Graduates Respondents				
1	Gender	Male	5	62.5
		Female	3	37.5
		Total	8	100
2	Age	21-25 years	8	100
		Total	8	100
3	Graduate Force	2018	1	12.5
		2019	1	12.5
		2020	3	37.5
		2021	3	37.5
		Total	8	100
4	Position	Civil Servant	2	25.0
		Private Employees	4	50.0
		Entrepreneur	2	25.0
		Total	8	100
5	Length of Work	1-5 years	8	100
		Total	8	100
Supervisor Respondents				
1	Gender	Male	2	50.0
		Female	2	50.0
		Total	4	100
2	Position	Senior Manager	1	25.0
		HRD/Recruitment Team	1	25.0
		Staffing Department	2	50.0
		Total	4	100

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Based on in Table 1, there were 8 graduates and 4 supervisors who were mostly male. The average age of graduate respondents is between 21-25 years. Most of them come from the 2020 and 2021 graduate force and most of them work as private employees and have worked for 1-5 years.

B. Result of Questionnaire with Graduate Respondents

The following is an overview of the result of a closed questionnaire from graduate respondents Management Study Program who have worked either as civil servants, private employees, or entrepreneurs in Makassar City regarding the level of relevance of the competence of the Management Study Program graduates to employment needs.

Table II. Questionnaire Results from Graduate Respondents

No	Indicator	Answer			
		R	QR	LR	IR
1	Speed of graduates getting jobs based on skills	9	4	5	6
2	Job profile, position, or workload	11	29	6	2
3	Abilities to complete work	12	19	1	0
4	Benefit from programmed courses in lectures	7	33	15	1
Total		39	85	27	9

The results of the answers from graduates were analyzed based on the relevance level that has been made by the

researcher. The following level of relevance is shown in Table III.

Table III. Category Level of Relevance

Category of Relevance	Relevance Assessment
R	Relevant
QR	Quite Relevant
LR	Less Relevant
IR	Irrelevant

(source : Arikunto,2016;Sahade,2021)

From the questionnaire given to graduate respondents, there were 20 questions from four indicators, namely, the first indicator was about the speed with which graduates got jobs based on skill with a total of 3 questions. The second indicator is about the job profile, position, and workload as many as 6 questions. The third indicator about the ability to complete work with as many as 4 questions. And finally, the fourth indicator about the benefits from programmed courses in lectures with 7 questions.

In the first indicator, the number of questions is 3, with 8 respondents so there are a total of 24 answer choices. Based on Table II, there were 9 answers that chose the R category or 37.5% of the total answers; 4 answers chose the QR category or 16.7% of the total answers; 5 answers chose the LR category or 20.83% of the total answers, and 6 answers chose the IR category or 25% of total answers. In this case, the relevance of graduates of the Management Study Program to employment in terms of the speed with which graduates

got jobs based on the skill stated is relevant with the majority of respondents answering R, which is 37.5% of the total answer choices.

For the second indicator there are 6 questions answered by 8 respondents so there are 48 answer choices. As seen in Table II, there were 11 answers that chose the R category or 22.91% of the total answers; 29 answers chose the QR category or 60.41% of the total answer choices; 6 answer choices chose the LR category or 12.5% of the total answer choices and 1 answer choose the IR category or 2.08% of the total answer choices. This shows the relevance of the Management Study Program to employment in terms of job profile, position and workload which quite relevant with the majority of respondents answering QR, namely 60.41% of the total choices.

In the third indicator, the number of questions is 4, answered by 8 respondents so there are 32 answer choices. Based on Table II, there are 12 answer choices that have the R category

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or 37.5% of the total answer choices; 19 answers chose the QR category or 59.38% of the total answers; 1 answer chooses the LR category or 12% of the total answer choices and no one chooses the IR category answers. This shows that the level of relevance of Management Study Program graduates with employment in terms of their ability to complete work is stated to be quite relevant, as seen from the majority of respondents' answers choosing the QR category, namely 59.38% of the total answer choices.

And finally, the fourth indicator with 7 questions answered by 8 respondents so that there are a total of 56 answer choices. As seen in Table II, there are 7 answers that chose the R category or 12.5% of the total answer choices; 33 answers chose the QR category or 58.93% of the total answer choices; 15 answers chose the LR category or 26.78% of the total answer choices and 1 answer chose the IR category or 1.85% of the total answer choices. In this case, the level of relevance of Management Study Program graduates to employment in terms of the benefits from programmed courses in lectures is stated to be quite relevant, seen from the majority of respondents answers who chose the QR category, namely 58.93% of the total answer choices.

Based on the result of data analysis of the four indicators, with four levels of relevance, namely R (Relevant); QR (Quite Relevant); LR (Less Relevant); and IR (Irrelevant) then the overall result of the answer choices is $20 \times 8 = 160$ choices. In which category R as a whole, there are 39 answers or 24.38%; 85 total answers chose the QR category 53.12%; 27 total answers or 16.78% chose the LR category and 9 total answers or 5.72% chose the IR category. Thus, it can be concluded that the level of relevance of Management Study Program graduates to employment is stated to be quite relevant, as evidenced by the majority of respondents choosing the QR answer or 53.12% of the total answers.

As for some input and suggestions from graduates of the Management Study Program on the Department for graduates to easily get jobs, namely:

1. Increase lectures in the form of internships so that you gain experience before entering the world of work.
2. Final year students are given training and certification based on their major background so that it the graduates' Curriculum Vitae when applying for a job.
- 3.

C. Result of Interview with Supervisor Respondents

Based on the results of interviews with supervisor respondents, answers were obtained in a descriptive form containing input, opinions, and views of the Management Study Program graduate so that they are easily accepted in the world of work. The following are some conclusions that can be drawn from the answers respondents to the questions given:

1. There are two paths for graduates of the Management Study Program to be accepted into government, namely:

a) Official Path for ASN acceptance; and b) Contract Labor.

2. For graduates who want to work in the private sector, emphasis is placed on the soft skills they have in accordance with the position being applied for.
3. Things to consider if alumni have: a) responsibility in managing a company or organization; b) able to manage projects; c) ability to manage finances and budgets; and d) have expertise in administration.
4. Factors supporting management graduates getting a job, namely: work experience/internship, organizational experience, soft skill competence, teamwork ability, project management ability, self-management ability, and competent certification.

V. CONCLUSION

From the research results regarding the level of relevance of competence of Management graduates at Makassar State University and the supporting factors to the need for employment, it can be concluded as follows:

1. The research results from the level of relevance between Management Study Program Graduates and employment were 53.12%. It means that the Management Study Program Graduates and employment are the categorization of 41-60% or can be said to be quite relevant.
2. Factors supporting Management Study Program graduates getting jobs based on personnel section, HDR, or recruitment team information namely, work experience/internship, organizational experience, soft skills, teamwork ability, project management ability, and competency certification.

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